

THE INFLUENCE OF TRANSVERSE SHEAR AND ROTATIONAL INERTIA
ON THE DYNAMIC INSTABILITY OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the influence of transverse shear and the rotational inertia on the dynamic buckling of laminated composite plates is analyzed. In the formulation of the governing equations and their solutions, the effects of initial imperfections and the ply-angle of the laminated plates are also considered. These factors had not been considered in our previous paper that was published on ICCS-4, 1987 (Ref. [1]). Here, we use the principle of Hamilton to get the nonlinear general equations for the dynamic buckling of laminated plates. Some symmetrically angle-ply laminated plates are computed as examples to illustrate those effects. Results show that the consideration of the above described influence is important for the analysis of dynamic buckling of the laminated composite plates.

INTRODUCTION

Many laminated composite plate structures are used under the conditions of in-plane dynamic loading, this causes dynamic buckling of the plate structures. In many cases, dynamic instability of the structure often induce serious collapse of some whole structures. This is an important problem in the aeronautical and astronautical as well as naval structures. But, because of the complexity of the problem, up to now only a few research works are relating to this important field. Though some works are discussing the dynamic unstable problems of plate structures, most of them mainly considered only the dynamic response of the plates under the condition of impact loading or vibration. Recently, Birman [2] proposed a simple criterion for the effects of unsymmetrical lamination of the plate on the distribution of unstable regions. Ref. [3] studied the dynamic instability of laminated plates under in-plane parametric vibration. They used finite strip method to solve the dynamic unstable region. But in [3], the governing equations were linear, and the effect of longitudinal inertia force and the influence of transverse shear were neglected. Last year (1987), we contributed a paper on the ICCS-4 (Ref. [1]), in which we considered the resonance of parametric vibration for laminated composite plates under longitudinal compression. We used nonlinear governing equations and the large deflection solutions of steady parametric vibration to determine the unstable regions. The influence of longitudinal inertia force on the dynamic buckling behavior of the laminated plates is considered. Results show that the effect is noticeable, and for antisymmetric anisotropic laminated plate the coupling effect plays an important role in the analysis of dynamic instability of plates. In this paper, we will show some advanced results that includes the influence of transverse shear and the rotational inertia as well as the effect of initial imperfections on the dynamic buckling behavior of laminated composite plates.

FUNDAMENTAL EQUATIONS

Consider a clamped or simply supported rectangular thin plate with the length a and width b . If this plate is an angle-ply laminated composite plate, according to [4,5], the physical equations of stress-strain relations are :

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \\ \kappa \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \begin{Bmatrix} Q_x \\ Q_y \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{55} & A_{45} \\ A_{45} & A_{44} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{zx} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{zx} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \phi_x + w_{,x} \\ \phi_y + w_{,y} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The in-plane loading acting on the plate is :

$$P_x = N_{o_x} + N_{tx} \cos \theta t, \quad P_y = N_{o_y} + N_{ty} \cos \theta t, \quad P_{xy} = N_{o_{xy}} + N_{txy} \cos \theta t \quad (2)$$

The total potential energy Π and kinetic energy T are :

$$\Pi = U + V, \quad T = \int_0^a \int_0^b \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (1/2) \rho [(\bar{u}_{,t})^2 + (\bar{v}_{,t})^2 + (w_{,t})^2] dx dy \quad (3)$$

where, h is the thickness of the plate; $\bar{u} = u + z \cdot \phi_x$, $\bar{v} = v + z \cdot \phi_y$, $\bar{w} = w$, are displacements. According to Hamilton Principle, get :

$$\delta \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (T - \Pi) dt = 0 \quad (4)$$

Take the variations of u, v, w, ϕ_x, ϕ_y , get:

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{(\rho h)^3}{12} \phi_{x,tt} - Q_x + M_{x,x} + M_{xy,y} &= 0, & -\frac{(\rho h)^3}{12} \phi_{y,tt} - Q_y + M_{xy,x} + M_{y,y} &= 0 \\ N_{x,x} + N_{xy,y} + \rho h u_{,tt} &= 0, & N_{xy,x} + N_{y,y} - \rho h v_{,tt} &= 0 \\ (N_x + P_{o_x} + P_{tx} \cos \theta t) \lambda w_{,xx} + 2(N_{xy} + P_{o_{xy}} + P_{txy} \cos \theta t) \lambda w_{,xy} + \\ (N_y + P_{o_y} + P_{ty} \cos \theta t) \lambda w_{,yy} + N_{x,x} \lambda w_{,x} + N_{xy,x} \lambda w_{,y} + N_{xy,y} \lambda w_{,x} + \\ N_{y,y} w_{,y} - Q_{x,x} - Q_{y,y} \rho h w_{,tt} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The above equations include the factors of in-plane inertia force, rotational inertia, transverse shear deformation, initial imperfections and etc, so they have the generality for using in the laminated plates with any ply-angles.

Consider a simply supported symmetric cross-ply laminated plate, boundary conditions :

$$x=0, w=M_x=u=N_{xy}=0; \quad y=0, b, w=M_y=v=N_{xy}=0; \quad x=a, w=M_x=N_{xy}=0, \int_0^b N_x dy = -(N_o + N_t \cos \theta t) b$$

Take the deflection function w and the initial imperfection function w_o as [7] :

$$w = f(t) \sin \frac{\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{\pi y}{b}; \quad w_o = f_o \sin \frac{\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{\pi y}{b} \quad (6)$$

Use Galerkin method, get the following equations including the effect of imperfection:

$$f''(t) + \Omega^2 (1 - 2\mu \cos \theta t) \cdot f(t) + 2\gamma f_o^2 \cdot f(t) + 3\gamma f_o f^2(t) + \gamma f^3(t) = \frac{w_o^2}{N} (N_o + N_t \cos \theta t) f_o \quad (7)$$

$$\text{where, } \Omega^2 = \omega^2 (1 - \frac{N_o}{N_{cr}}), \quad \mu = \frac{1}{2} \frac{N_t}{N_{cr} - N_o}, \quad \omega^2 = \frac{\pi^4}{ma^2} [D_{11} + \alpha^4 D_{22} + 2\alpha^2 (D_{12} + 2D_{66})] \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\omega^2}{N_{cr}} = \frac{\pi^2}{ma^2} (1 + \alpha^2 \frac{A_{12}}{A_{11}}), \quad m = \rho h, \quad \alpha = \frac{a}{b}, \quad \gamma = \frac{\pi^4}{16ma^4} (A_{11} + 3\alpha^2 A_{22}) (1 - \frac{A_{12}^2}{A_{11}A_{22}})$$

When consider the effect of transverse shear, use the same method, and can get:

$$f''(t) + \Omega^2 (1 - 2\mu \cos \theta t) f(t) + 2k [f(t) f''(t) + (f'(t))^2] f(t) + \gamma f^3(t) + 2\epsilon f'(t) + 2\epsilon_L f(t) [f'(t)]^2 = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\text{where, } \Omega = \omega \sqrt{1 - (N_o/N_{cr})}, \quad \mu = \frac{N_o}{2(N_{cr} - N_o)}, \quad \omega^2 = \frac{\pi}{\rho h} \left[\frac{A_{55}}{a} (\phi_1 + \frac{\pi}{a}) + \frac{A_{44}}{b} (\psi_1 + \frac{\pi}{b}) \right]$$

$$N_{cr} = \frac{A_{11} b^2}{A_{12} \lambda \pi} \left[\frac{A_{55}}{a} (\phi_1 + \frac{\pi}{a}) + \frac{A_{44}}{b} (\psi_1 + \frac{\pi}{b}) \right], \quad \gamma = \frac{\pi^4}{16\phi h} (A_{11} A_{22} - A_{12}^2) \left(\frac{1}{a^4 A_{22}} + \frac{3}{b^4 A_{11}} \right)$$

$$\phi_1 = \frac{\pi}{\beta} \left[\frac{A_{55}}{a} (A_{44} + \frac{\pi^2}{2} D_{22} + \frac{\pi^2}{2} D_{66}) - \frac{A_{44}}{b} (\frac{\pi^2}{ab} D_{12} + \frac{\pi^2}{a} D_{66}) \right], \quad \omega_L = \frac{\pi}{2a} \sqrt{A_{11}/\rho h} \quad (10)$$

$$\psi_1 = \frac{\pi}{\beta} \left[\frac{A_{44}}{b} (A_{55} + \frac{\pi^2}{2} D_{11} + \frac{\pi^2}{2} D_{66}) - \frac{A_{55}}{a} \frac{\pi}{ab} (D_{12} + D_{66}) \right], \quad k = -\frac{\pi \lambda}{32} \left[\frac{3A_{12}}{A_{11} b^2} + \frac{A_{12}}{A_{22} a^2} + \frac{1}{2a^2} - \frac{3}{2b^2} \right]$$

$$\beta = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{1}{a^2} (D_{12} + D_{66})^2 - (A_{55} + \frac{\pi^2}{2} D_{11} + \frac{\pi^2}{2} D_{66}) (A_{44} + \frac{\pi^2}{2} D_{22} + \frac{\pi^2}{2} D_{66})$$

$$\delta = \text{tg} \frac{\pi \theta}{2\omega_L} \left[\frac{8\omega_L \pi}{\theta a^2} (1 + \frac{b^2 A_{11}}{2A_{12}}) - \rho h \frac{4\theta b^2 \omega_L}{\pi a A_{12}} \right] / \left[\left(\frac{2\pi}{a} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{\pi \theta}{2\omega_L a} \right)^2 \right] - \frac{b^2 A_{11}}{2A_{12}}$$

here, ϕ_1, ψ_1 represent the effect of transverse shear, δ is the vibration function for longitudinal resonance. For symmetrical angle-ply laminated plates, if effects of transverse shear and rotational inertia force are neglected, get the following equations to analyze the influence of the ply-angle of the laminated plates.

$$f''(t) + \Omega^2 (1 - 2\mu\phi \cos \theta t) f(t) + 2kf(t) [f(t) \cdot f''(t) + (f'(t))^2] + \gamma f^3(t) + 2\epsilon f'(t) + 2\epsilon_L f(t) [f'(t)]^2 = 0 \quad (11)$$

where, $\Omega = \omega \sqrt{1 - N_0/N_{cr}}$, $\mu = \frac{N_t}{2(N_{cr} - N_0)}$, $\omega^2 = \frac{\pi ab}{8k_2} \left[\frac{D_{11}}{4} + \frac{2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})}{a^2 b^2} + \frac{D_{22}}{b^4} \right]$

$$N_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 ab}{\lambda(b/a + c_0 a/b)} \left[\frac{D_{11}}{4} + \frac{2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})}{a^2 b^2} + \frac{D_{22}}{b^4} \right], \quad \gamma = \frac{\lambda^2 \pi^4}{128k_2} \left(\frac{b}{a_{11} a^3} + \frac{a}{a_{22} b^3} \right)$$

$$k_1 = \frac{2\lambda}{128} \rho h \left[\frac{b^3 (a_{12}^2 + a_{16}^2)}{2a_{11}^2 a^3} + \frac{a^3 (a_{12}^2 + a_{26}^2)}{2a_{22}^2 b^3} - \frac{a_{12}^2 a}{a_{22} b} - \frac{a_{12}^2 b}{a_{11} a} - \frac{5}{4} \left(\frac{b}{a} + \frac{a}{b} \right) + \frac{13\pi^2}{3} \left(\frac{b}{a} + \frac{a}{b} \right) \right]$$

$$k = k_1 / (2k_2), \quad k_2 = \frac{\rho h}{8} \left[\frac{\pi^2 h^2}{12} \left(\frac{b}{a} + \frac{a}{b} \right) + ab \right] \quad (12)$$

$$k_3 = \frac{\lambda \rho h}{16} \left[\left(a_{12} - \frac{a_{16}^2}{a_{66}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{12}^2 b^3}{a_{11}^2 a} + ab - \frac{13}{3} \pi^2 ab \right) + \left(a_{11} - \frac{a_{16}^2}{a_{66}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{12}^2 a^3}{a_{22}^2 b} + ab - \frac{13}{3} \pi^2 ab \right) \right] \cdot N_t \theta$$

$$k_4 = \frac{\lambda \rho h}{16} \left[\left(a_{22} - \frac{a_{26}^2}{a_{66}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{12}^2 b^3}{a_{11}^2 a} + ab - \frac{13}{3} \pi^2 ab \right) + \left(a_{12} - \frac{a_{16}^2}{a_{66}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{12}^2 a^3}{a_{22}^2 b} + ab - \frac{13}{3} \pi^2 ab \right) \right] a N_t \theta$$

In Eqs. (10), (11), the terms $2\epsilon f(t)$ and $2\epsilon_L f'(t)^2$ denote the damping factor; a_{ij} ($i, j = 1, 2, 6$) are elements of the matrix A .

SOLUTIONS AND NUMERICAL RESULTS

Eq. (7) is an equation of forced vibration, its solution with period T can be taken as

$$f(t) = b_0 + \sum_{k=2,4,6,\dots} \left(a_k \sin \frac{k\theta t}{2} + b_k \cos \frac{k\theta t}{2} \right) \quad (13)$$

Substitute into Eq. (7), use Liapouf principle, and ignor the unstable solution, get:

$$\left(1 + \frac{2\gamma}{\Omega^2} f_0^2 \right) b_0 - \mu A + \frac{3\gamma}{2\Omega^2} (f_0 + b_0) A^2 = \frac{N_0}{N_{cr} - N_0} f_0, \quad -2\mu b_0 + \frac{\theta \gamma}{\Omega^2} f_0 b_0 A + (1 - 4n^2 + \frac{2\gamma}{\Omega^2} f_0^2 + \frac{3\gamma}{4\Omega^2} A^2) A = 2\mu f_0 \quad (14)$$

here, $A = a^2 + b^2$, $n = \frac{\theta}{2\Omega}$. Numerical results show in Figs. 1, 2 and 3. Fig. 1 shows that when the disturbance frequency θ/Ω increases to a critical value $\theta_0 = (\theta/\Omega)_D$, the amplitude A will jump suddenly, the jumping value is DE , and after that the amplitude A will increase linearly with the increasing value of θ/Ω . This linear period of A can be represented approximately by $A = 2n \sqrt{(3\gamma)/(4\Omega^2)}$. Fig. 2 shows the influence of initial imperfections f_0 . When f_0 is increasing, the critical values of $\theta_0 = (\theta/\Omega)_{cr}$ that characterize the amplitude jumping will increase significantly, together with the increasing of amplitude jumping value. Fig. 3 shows as the value of the disturbance frequency θ/Ω increases to a certain big value, the effect of initial imperfections on the dynamic deflections of the laminated plate can be ignored.

For Eq. (9), take a solution of parametric vibration with period $2T$, thus get:

$$f(t) = \sum_{k=1,3,5,\dots} \left(a_k \sin \frac{k\theta t}{2} + b_k \cos \frac{k\theta t}{2} \right) \quad (15)$$

Substitute into Eq. (9), get a set of equations relate to coefficients a and b :

$$\left(1 + \mu\phi - n^2 \right) a_1 - \frac{nd_1}{\pi} b_1 + \left(\frac{3\gamma}{4\Omega^2} a_1 - \frac{nd_1^2}{\pi} b_1 - kn^2 a_1 \right) A^2 = 0, \quad \left(1 - \mu\phi - n^2 \right) b_1 + \frac{nd_1}{\pi} a_1 + \left(\frac{3\gamma}{4\Omega^2} b_1 + \frac{nd_1^2}{\pi} a_1 - kn^2 b_1 \right) A^2 = 0 \quad (16)$$

where, $d = \frac{2\pi\epsilon}{\Omega}$, $d_1 = \frac{2\pi\epsilon_L}{\Omega}$, $A = a^2 + b^2$. The main unstable region can be determined by the above Eq. (16), its numerical results show in Fig. 4. The amplitude formula is:

$$A = \sqrt{\left[P(1 - n^2) - \frac{n^2}{2} d \cdot d_1 + \sqrt{\mu^2 \phi^2 \left(P^2 + \frac{n^2}{2} d_1^2 \right) - \frac{n^2}{2} (Pd + d_1^2 + d_1^2 n^2)^2} \right] / \left(P + \frac{n^2}{2} d_1^2 \right)}, \quad P = kn^2 - \frac{3\gamma}{2} \quad (17)$$

Fig. 4 shows π that transverse shear π makes the region of longitudinal resonance to move away from the region of parametric resonance, thus decreases the possibility of duplication for these two resonance regions. This means the consideration of transverse shear deformation makes the laminated plates to be more flexible, that lowers the values of N_{cr} , ω , and Ω , and increase the longitudinal resonance frequency $\omega_L = \omega/2\Omega$. In this sense, transverse shear increase the dynamic stability of the plates. But, as N_{cr} is lowered, stimulating coefficient μ is increased, this makes the unstable region to be wider, and that decreases the dynamic stability of the plate. These two

are coupling together, should be analyzed synthetically. Fig.5 shows that the effect of transverse shear makes principal parametric resonance curves moving to the larger value of frequency. Figs.6,7 and 8 show the influence of ply angles $\alpha(^{\circ})$ on μ^* , A_{\max} and L_{\max} respectively. Here, μ^* is the critical stimulating coefficient, A_{\max} is the maximum amplitude, L_{\max} is the maximum traction depth of principal parametric vibration. Fig.6 shows when ply angle of the reinforced fiber approaches the direction of loading (0°), the value of μ^* will be larger, this represents better dynamic stability of the plate. Fig.7 shows the lowest value of A_{\max} happens on the ply angles near 0° and 90° , and the maximum value is near 45° . This means the ply-angle of 45° should be avoid. L_{\max} denotes the existing region of parametric resonance, the smaller value of L_{\max} , the better dynamic stability of the plate will be. Fig.8 shows the relation between L_{\max} and ply-angles. The synthetic analysis of the above three factors for the dynamic stability of the laminated plates concludes that the best ply angle is 0° that coincides with the loading direction, the worst ply angle is 90° . The material constants used in the computation of Figs.1 to 3 are: T300/5208 cross-ply symmetric laminated plates, 4 layers, thickness $h=0.4\text{cm}$, $\mu=0.3$, $f_0=0.1$, $P_0=0.5P^{\text{cr}}$. Material constants used for Figs.5 and 6 are listed in Table 1(Carbon/epoxy), for Figs.6,7,8 are listed in Table 2 (Glass/epoxy), 3 layers($n=3$), imperfection $\lambda=1.2$.

Table 1 Material constants of carbon/epoxy (used for Figs.5 and 6)

E_1 (kg/mm^2)	E_2 (kg/mm^2)	G_{12} (kg/mm^2)	G_{23} (kg/mm^2)	G_{31} (kg/mm^2)	ρ (kg/mm^3)	μ_{12}	a (mm)	b (mm)	h (mm)
2.1×10^5	1.05×10^4	6.3×10^3	4.2×10^3	6.3×10^3	1.6×10^{-6}	0.28	150	100	2

Table 2 Material constants of glass/epoxy (used for Figs.6,7 and 8)

E_1 (kg/mm^2)	E_2 (kg/mm^2)	G_{12} (kg/mm^2)	ρ (kg/mm^3)	μ_{12}	γ_f	a (mm)	b (mm)	h (mm)
3.567×10^4	1.0388×10^4	4.6354×10^4	1.86×10^{-6}	0.33	0.50	150	100	1.2

REFERENCES

1. Zhou Cheng-ti and Wang Li-tung, An analysis of dynamic Instability on Laminated Composite Plates, 4th Intern. Conf. on Composite Structures (ICCS-4), Paisley College Scotland, 27-29 July (1987). (will be published in Intern. J. of Comp. Structures).
2. Birman, V., Mech. Res. Commun., 12(2) (1985), 81.
3. Srinivasan, R.S., 24(2), (1986), 233.
4. Jones, R.M., Mechanics of Composite Materials, McGraw-Hill, (1975).
5. Wang Zhen-ming, Liu Guo-xi and Lu Ming-shen, Applied Math. and Mech., 3(1) (1982).
6. Bolotin, V.V., Dynamic stability of elastic system, Moscow (1956), (in Russian).
7. Zhou Cheng-ti, Elasticity of Composite Materials, "Lecture for Applied Mathematics and Mechanics", 28th Lecture held in Kun-Ming, China, (1983), (in Chinese).

Fig.1

Fig.2

Fig.3(a)

Fig.3(b)

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Fig. 8